

Paper on the marine ecosystem classification for surface and near seabed waters in Europe

Deliverable 2.6

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.6 overview

The present document details the data acquisition and computational procedures involved in Deliverable 2.6 of MPA Europe. It provides a **depth-integrated marine ecosystem classification for Europe** (0-2,500 m depth and seabed) using a wide range of spatially complete and standardised environmental data that reflect both ecosystem conditions and functioning.

The classification of ecosystems considered clustering algorithms fitting high-resolution environmental data for European seas (Environmental data preparation; Deliverable 2.1, WP2; Assis et al, 2023). In this scope and for the purposes of the MPA Europe project, ‘ecosystems’ are defined as “**enduring, spatially bounded environments where biological and energy interactions are greater within than with other ecosystems**” (Zhao et al. 2019). The information provided contributes to policy-relevant research focusing on MPA designation, in particular, mapping biodiversity patterns at an ecosystem level. It will feed the main subsequent tasks of Prioritisation (WP5), which aim to design (prioritise locations for) MPA networks using a systematic conservation planning approach maximising the coverage of the marine biodiversity.

Because any classification may be influenced by the scope of the variables used, we conducted a global classification analysis to include the full range of conditions that exist in the oceans. This is attached as an Appendix.

Methods

Data preparation

The environmental data used in cluster analysis were derived from [Deliverable 2.1](#) (WP2, Assis et al., 2023). These data comprise environmental data layers with a 0.25 degrees resolution (approx. 27 km at the equator) for European seas. They are spatially complete and standardised, generated with information from the Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast and the Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast, which are two pre-processed re-analyses of [Copernicus Marine Service](#) that integrate and assimilate a comprehensive range of satellite and in-situ data (Assis et al., 2023).

Nine meaningful environmental variables for the waters of European seas were selected. Eight of them were also used for surface waters ([Deliverable 2.3](#), Campoy et al., 2023a), namely, dissolved molecular oxygen (mmol m⁻³), nitrate (mmol m⁻³), ocean temperature (°C), pH, phosphate (mmol m⁻³), phytoplankton (mmol m⁻³), salinity and sea ice cover (%). The mixed layer depth (m) was also included for this analysis. Data were represented as the averaged values over the decade 2010-2019, except the sea ice cover, for which the maximum value for the 2010-2019 period was used. Thus, the ecosystem classification reflects the long-term enduring climatology that drives the distribution of species and habitats as distinct from seasonal and annual variation that affect population abundance.

To carry out a depth-integrated (three-dimensional) approach, 15 data layers were included for each environmental variable, corresponding to depths from 0 to 2,500 m (0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250, 500, 750, 1,000, 1,500, 2,000 and 2,500 m depth, [Deliverable 2.5](#), Campoy et al. 2024) and the near seabed ([Deliverable 2.4](#), Campoy et al. 2023b). The so-called near seabed layer refers to the water layer that closely follows the topography of the ocean floor, hence it has a variable depth depending on underlying features such as the continental shelf, slope, abyssal plains, or seamounts, among others. Data layers for depth between 2,500 m and near seabed were excluded in these analyses due to the lack of information and high level of uncertainty that it would cause. In the case of sea ice cover, only a data layer for the 0 m depth was included, while for other depths, it was set to zero. The mixed layer depth was also modified to follow the depth-integration format of the rest of the variables. Thus, cells above the mixed layer were assigned a zero value, while cells below the mixed layer were assigned a value of one. The correlation among selected variables was assessed through the Pearson's correlation coefficient (Table 1).

Data were standardised using Z-scores. This procedure involved adjusting each data point to be centred on the mean and scaled based on the standard deviation. Standardisation with Z-scores is necessary for removing scale bias, ensuring an unbiased interpretation of results, and facilitating comparisons between variables. Following a similar approach developed for the classifications of marine ecosystem in Europe for surface ([Deliverable 2.3](#), Campoy et al. 2023a) and near seabed waters ([Deliverable 2.4](#), Campoy et al. 2023b), Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was further performed to mitigate inter-variable correlations and reduce data dimensionality. PCA is a multivariate technique that transforms the original variables into a new set of orthogonal variable dimensions called principal components. The initial six principal components were selected, which collectively explained 95 % of the variance in the data (Table 2). By retaining these components, information was effectively captured while reducing the complexity of the dataset.

The PCA led to a data matrix comprising 298,655 rows (i.e., linked to the 0.25 resolution cells) and six columns (i.e., PC1-6). The dataset underwent normalization by scaling each variable to a range between 0 and 1 (Figure 1). This preprocessing step ensured that variables with different scales contributed equally to subsequent analyses. By eliminating the influence of variable scales, the normalized data provides a foundation for accurate and meaningful interpretations, especially when

employing algorithms sensitive to input feature magnitudes, such as clustering and distance-based methods.

Data clustering

The k-means clustering approach was utilised to find structure in the data. This is a popular unsupervised machine learning algorithm used for partitioning a dataset into a predefined number of distinct, non-overlapping clusters. It works by iteratively assigning data points to the nearest cluster centroid and then recalculating the centroids based on the mean of the points assigned to each cluster. This process continues until convergence when the centroids no longer change significantly. Thus, it is suitable for clustering data points with numerical features into k clusters, where k is a user-specified parameter. It is an efficient method known for its simplicity in cluster assignment.

K-means algorithms seek to minimise the within-cluster sum of squared (WSS) distances, i.e., between each data point and the centroid of its assigned cluster, while maximising the between-cluster sum of squared (BSS) distances, i.e. between the centroids of all clusters and the overall mean of the data. The total sum of squares (TSS=WSS+BSS) represents the total variability in the data without considering the clustering. WSS, BSS and TSS are metrics used to evaluate the performance and quality of the clustering. Taking this into account, we have implemented a divisive hierarchical k-means approach. In this approach, k=2 is initially specified, and after running the algorithm, we iterate it for the cluster with the higher WSS. This process can be repeated until all clusters represent individual cells, resulting in the number of clusters (k) being equal to the number of observations in the data matrix.

The hierarchical k-means clustering was applied to the data using the *kmeans* function from the R package *stats*, utilising the Hartigan-Wong algorithm (Hartigan & Wong 1979). This algorithm starts by choosing k initial random centroids and assigning each data point to the nearest centroid. When all points have been assigned, the cluster centroids are updated. During subsequent iterations, each point is individually evaluated and reassigned to a different cluster based on the decrease in the sum of squares distances. Then, the centroids are updated until they stabilize, or the maximum number of iterations reached. In this case, a wide maximum of 500 iterations were established. Since the resulting clusters are heavily influenced by the choosing of initial centroids, i.e., the algorithm might get stuck in a local optimum, 100 random initial centroid assignments were allowed. In addition, the clustering was repeated three times to ensure that the results remained unchanged (Table 3).

The above-described approach is known as a hard partition because the cluster membership is strict, i.e., each data point belongs to a single cluster. The alternative is a fuzzy partition, where every data point has a probability of closeness (in a range of 0 to 1) to each cluster. This approach is more realistic than hard partition since data points can belong to multiple clusters with varying degrees of likelihood, allowing for the representation of uncertainty and overlapping patterns in the cluster assignments. To incorporate fuzzy partition in the analyses, the fuzzy c-means algorithm was implemented through the *c-means* function of the R package *e1071* (Meyer et al. 2023). On each step of the divisive hierarchical approach, the fuzzy probabilities of each data point were recalculated for the full dataset and the new cluster assignments.

One crucial aspect of clustering is the specification of the number of clusters (k). We have circumvented this challenge using hierarchical k-means clustering. Although all obtained levels of clustering are valid and comparable, some results are notably more optimal. The criterion for this optimality depends on the metric selected. In this case, we have chosen to combine the results from the sum of squares (WSS and BSS) with the silhouette score. The silhouette score measures how similar an object is to its own cluster (intra-cluster similarity) compared to other clusters (inter-cluster dissimilarity). It is calculated as the average silhouette coefficient for all points in the dataset, providing a way to assess the quality of clustering by quantifying the compactness and separation of

the clusters. It ranges from -1 to 1. A score closer to +1 indicates that the clustering configuration is appropriate, with well-defined clusters. Conversely, a score near -1 suggests that the clustering may have been inappropriate, with points possibly assigned to the wrong clusters. A score around 0 indicates overlapping clusters or points at the decision boundary between clusters. Due to computational resource limitations imposed by the dataset size, 100 random samples of size 1,000 were iteratively generated to calculate the silhouette score from the R package *fpc* (Hennig 2023). This approach has enabled us to identify the **three most representative hierarchical levels**. For the purposes of this deliverable, we will focus on one of them (**four ecosystems**), although a different selection may also be suitable for other objectives.

Results

The three-dimensional mapping was achieved by clustering of nine environmental variables summarized into six principal components. The hierarchical k-means clustering resulted in an exponential increase in cluster compactness and separation, as evidenced by the decreasing WSS and the corresponding increasing BSS (Table 3 and Figure 2). The selected clustering levels led to **four (k=4), seven (k=7) and 13 (k=13) ecosystems**. These points exhibit peaks in the silhouette score and a notable increase in WSS (accompanied by a decrease in BSS). For instance, k=4 is the first point where WSS exceeds BSS, indicating better-defined clusters compared to k=2 and k=3. K=5 through 10 show linear increase in WSS/BSS values, but k=7 exhibits the highest silhouette score. Afterward, the WSS/BSS values continue to grow very slowly near the asymptote, and the silhouette score peaks at k=13 before decreasing (Figure 2). On the other hand, the environmental differences between ecosystems became smaller at increasing clustering levels (Figure 3).

Four ecosystems arise at the first selected hierarchical level with a different depth extent (Figure 4). Ecosystems 2 and 3 are found in all depths with different proportions (0.27-95.78 and 1.22-82.41, respectively). The bigger ecosystem is the 2, which reaches its bigger extent at 250 m, where it occupies 95.78 % of the surface. This contrasts with ecosystem 1, which decreases with increasing depth, being completely absent below 250 m, except for the seabed layer, where all four ecosystems are represented. Ecosystem 4 is a deep ecosystem that only appears below 200 m depth. Interestingly, ecosystems 1 and 4 share greater environmental similarities with each other, as do ecosystems 2 and 3 (Figure 3).

The geographical extent of the four ecosystems is represented in Figure 5. Ecosystem 1 occupies the northern area of the European seas together with the Baltic Sea in surface waters. The rest is occupied by ecosystem 3 at this depth. Higher uncertainty levels arise around the areas occupied by the ecosystem 1 and the Black Sea, suggesting that these may be further subdivided in increasing hierarchical levels.

At 25 m depth, ecosystem 2 appears in disperse spots of the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea (Figure 5). This ecosystem starts to increase its proportion, expanding first in southern areas but occupying most of the territory at 250 m depth, except for some spots where ecosystem 3 still shows up. The areas with higher fuzziness concentrate in the Baltic and Black seas, as in surface waters, but also around the spots where ecosystem 2 emerges.

Below 250 m, the ecosystem 3 increases again, specially in southern areas of the Atlantic Ocean. Interestingly, the Black and Baltic seas form the ecosystem 1 from 25 to 100 m depth. Below, it gets restricted to the Black Sea. Ecosystem 4 only appears in the Black Sea below 250 m, also including the seabed layer, denoting a distinct environment. In addition, at 250 m, where ecosystem 1 is almost entirely restricted to the Black Sea, the fuzziness level decreases here. But when this is entirely represented by ecosystem 4, the fuzziness completely disappears in the Black Sea. Below 500 m,

higher fuzziness is concentrated in the South Atlantic, while in the seabed, it follows the limits of the ecosystems (Figure 5).

Ecosystems 1 to 3 cross the mixed layer depth, while ecosystem 4 is entirely below it. Some Sea ice cover is present on ecosystems 1 to 3, but most of it is on ecosystem 1. The distribution of the other seven environmental variables across ecosystems is represented in Figure 6. Ecosystems 2 and 3 exhibit moderate to high levels of nitrate, especially ecosystem 3, which has the higher values. Both ecosystems also have high dissolved oxygen levels, although ecosystem 1 has higher values. The similarities of these two ecosystems through the different environmental variables also explains Figure 3. Ecosystem 1 has very variable levels of nitrate, pH, phytoplankton, phosphate and salinity. In turn, Ecosystem 4, the deep ecosystem, is characterized by low nitrate, oxygen, phytoplankton and salinity, but high pH and very stable temperature. These main differences among the 4 ecosystems that place 2 and 3 on one side, and 1 and 4 on the other, are also reflected in higher clustering divisions (Figure 3, $k=7$ and $k=13$).

Conclusions

In summary, by selecting biologically meaningful environmental variables and applying k-means clustering analysis using a newly implemented divisive hierarchical approach, the current deliverable offers a robust depth-integrated classification of marine ecosystems in European waters, including the seabed. Four, seven and 13 well-defined clusters were chosen as the better resolved nested solutions within the hierarchy of cluster. In this case, four ecosystems were chosen as the primary solution for European waters, each associated with distinct environmental characteristics. These ecosystems offer valuable insights for policymakers and researchers, especially concerning MPA designation and biodiversity conservation and will be used for the prioritisation analyses. In this context, the other two solutions may be considered in the future to achieve a finer spatial resolution. The chosen validation metrics demonstrate the quality and reliability of these results, further underscoring their significance for the objectives of the MPA Europe project.

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Table 1. Pearson's correlation coefficient for the nine environmental variables selected: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (temp), pH, phosphate (phosph), phytoplankton (phyto), salinity, sea ice cover (sea ice) and mixed layer depth (mixed).

	Oxygen	Nitrate	Temp	pH	Phosph	Phyto	Salinity	Sea ice	Mixed
Oxygen	1	0.06	-0.62	-0.06	-0.38	0.26	-0.17	0.21	-0.28
Nitrate		1	-0.62	-0.60	0.24	-0.55	0.09	-0.04	0.33
Temp			1	0.12	-0.28	0.26	0.23	-0.15	-0.10
pH				1	0.31	0.19	-0.06	0.09	-0.18
Phosph					1	-0.26	-0.43	-0.04	0.20
Phyto						1	-0.26	0.11	-0.53
Salinity							1	-0.12	0.01
Sea ice								1	-0.22
Mixed									1

Table 2. Result of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The first six principal components (PC1-6) recovered 95 % of the variance in the data matrix (in **bold**).

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9
Standard deviation	1.60	1.40	1.29	0.97	0.90	0.81	0.54	0.27	0.20
Proportion of variance	0.28	0.22	0.18	0.10	0.09	0.07	0.03	0.01	0.00
Cumulative proportion	0.28	0.50	0.69	0.79	0.88	0.95	0.99	0.99	1.00

Table 3. Result for the first six clusters obtained to show the functioning of the divisive hierarchical k-means approach. TSS: Total sum of Squares. WSS: Within Sum of Squares. BSS: Between Sum of Squares. The number of clusters (N Clusters) increases one unit on each iteration, while TSS is kept constant, WSS decreases and BSS increases. The cluster size is given in number of cells. In red, the cluster subdivided in the consecutive step.

Level	N Clusters	TSS	WSS	BSS	Cluster size	Average area (m ²)
1	2	16,450	12,211	1,240	90,611 208,044	64,010,533
2	3		10,244	6,207	12,583 195,461 90,611	42,673,689
3	4		7,833	8,618	12,583 195,461 87,516 3,095	32,005,267
4	5		6,262	10,189	12,583 124,430 87,516 71,031 3,095	25,604,213
5	6		5,418	11,033	7,938 124,430 87,516 71,031 4,645 3,095	21,336,844

Figure 1. Variable distribution in the dataset before clustering. Each of the six variables corresponds to a principal component (PC1-6) preserved after PCA.

Figure 2. The upper panel displays the Total Sum of Squares (TSS), the Within-Cluster Sum of Squares (WSS), and the Between-Cluster Sum of Squares (BSS) for the first 100 clusters obtained using a divisive hierarchical k -means approach. The lower panel illustrates the silhouette values for each clustering solution, obtained from 100 random samples of 1,000 data points each. The number of clusters (N Clusters) increases by one unit in each iteration, from 2 to 100 clusters. The optimally selected clusters ($k=4$, $k=7$, and $k=13$) are marked with dotted lines.

Figure 3. Environmental Euclidean distance between the ecosystems obtained ($k=4$, $k=7$ and $k=13$).

Figure 4. Proportion of the four ecosystems obtained at each depth. Note that the seabed extends from the coast to the deep sea.

Surface

1 2 3

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

25 m depth

1 2 3

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

50 m depth

1 2 3

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

75 m depth

1 2 3

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

100 m depth

1 2 3

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

150 m depth

1 2 3

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

200 m depth

1 2 3 4

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

250 m depth

1 2 3 4

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

500 m depth

2 3 4

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

750 m depth

2 3 4

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

1,000 m depth

2 3 4

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

1,500 m depth

2 3 4

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

2,000 m depth

2 3 4

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

2,500 m depth

2 3

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

Seabed

1 2 3 4

0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00

Figure 5. Ecosystems obtained by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions in a divisive hierarchical k-means clustering of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 50 km wide for representation. All 15 depth layers included in the clustering are represented. Colour scale defines the four distinctive ecosystems identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.25 to 1) of each data point (right).

Figure 6. Environmental characteristics of the four identified ecosystems ($k=4$). Eight variables are represented: nitrate, dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), pH, phytoplankton, phosphate, salinity, and ocean temperature. The mixed layer depth and sea ice cover are not represented for being binary.

APPENDIX

A three-dimensional classification of ecosystems in the global oceans

Ana Navarro Campoy, Mark John Costello, Jorge Assis

Methods

Data preparation

The Bio-ORACLE computational pipeline (Assis et al., 2024) were utilized to produce climate layers for the ocean's surface level, at the global scale and at 0.25° resolution, per year, for the current baseline conditions (period 2010 to 2020) and the projected conditions of future change (period 2090 to 2100).

The Bio-ORACLE computational pipeline (Assis et al., 2024) were utilized to produce global environmental data layers at a 0.25 degrees resolution (approx. 27 km at the equator). They are spatially complete and standardised, generated with information from the Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast and the Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast, which are two pre-processed re-analyses of Copernicus Marine Service that integrate and assimilate a comprehensive range of satellite and in-situ data.

Nine biologically meaningful environmental variables were selected, namely, the average dissolved molecular oxygen (mmol m^{-3}), nitrate (mmol m^{-3}), pH, phosphate (mmol m^{-3}), and phytoplankton (mmol m^{-3}) over the period 2010-2018, and the average ocean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), salinity, and the mixed layer depth (m) over the period 2010-2019. Sea ice cover (%) was the maximum value for the 2010-2019 period. Thus, the ecosystem classification reflects the long-term enduring climatology that drives the distribution of species and habitats as distinct from seasonal and annual variation that affect population abundance.

To carry out a depth-integrated (three-dimensional) approach, the data layers were produced for a span of depths from 0 to 2,500 m (0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250, 500, 750, 1,000, 1,500, 2,000 and 2,500 m depth). In the case of sea ice cover, only a data layer for the 0 m depth was included, while for other depths, it was set to zero. On the other hand, the mixed layer depth was modified to follow the depth-integration format of the rest of the variables. Thus, cells above the mixed layer were assigned a zero value, while cells below the mixed layer were assigned a value of one.

The correlation among selected variables was assessed through the Pearson's correlation coefficient (Table 1).

Data were standardised using Z-scores. This procedure involved adjusting each data point to be centred on the mean and scaled based on the standard deviation. Standardisation with Z-scores is necessary for removing scale bias, ensuring an unbiased interpretation of results, and facilitating comparisons between variables.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was further performed to mitigate inter-variable correlations and reduce data dimensionality. PCA is a multivariate technique that transforms the original variables into a new set of orthogonal variable dimensions called principal components. The initial five principal components were selected, which collectively explained 95 % of the variance in the data (Table 2). By retaining these components, information was effectively captured while reducing the complexity of the dataset. The resultant data matrix had 9,421,072 observations of every variable across depths.

The dataset underwent normalization by scaling each variable to a range between 0 and 1 (Supplementary Figure 1). This preprocessing step ensured that variables with different scales contributed equally to subsequent analyses. By eliminating the influence of variable scales, the normalized data provides a foundation for accurate and meaningful interpretations, especially when employing algorithms sensitive to input feature magnitudes, such as clustering and distance-based methods.

Data clustering

The k-means clustering approach was utilised to find structure in the data. This is a popular unsupervised machine learning algorithm used for partitioning a dataset into a predefined number of distinct, non-overlapping clusters. It works by iteratively assigning data points to the nearest cluster centroid and then recalculating the centroids based on the mean of the points assigned to each cluster. This process continues until convergence when the centroids no longer change significantly. Thus, it is suitable for clustering data points with numerical features into k clusters, where k is a user-specified parameter. It is an efficient method known for its simplicity in cluster assignment.

K-means algorithms seek to minimise the within-cluster sum of squared (WSS) distances, i.e., between each data point and the centroid of its assigned cluster, while maximising the between-cluster sum of squared (BSS) distances, i.e. between the centroids of all clusters and the overall mean of the data. The total sum of squares (TSS=WSS+BSS) represents the total variability in the data without considering the clustering. WSS, BSS and TSS are metrics used to evaluate the performance and quality of the clustering. Taking this into account, we have implemented a divisive hierarchical k-means approach. In this approach, k=2 is initially specified, and after running the algorithm, we iterate it for the cluster with the higher WSS. This process can be repeated until all clusters represent individual cells, resulting in the number of clusters (k) being equal to the number of observations in the data matrix.

The hierarchical k-means clustering was applied to the data using the kmeans function from the R package stats, utilising the Hartigan-Wong algorithm (Hartigan & Wong 1979). This algorithm starts by choosing k initial random centroids and assigning each data point to the nearest centroid. When all points have been assigned, the cluster centroids are updated. During subsequent iterations, each point is individually evaluated and reassigned to a different cluster based on the decrease in the sum of squares distances. Then, the centroids are updated until they stabilize, or the maximum number of iterations reached. In this case, a wide maximum of 500 iterations were established. Since the resulting clusters are heavily influenced by the choosing of initial centroids, i.e., the algorithm might get stuck in a local optimum, 100 random initial centroid assignments were allowed. In addition, the clustering was repeated three times to ensure that the results remained unchanged (Table 3).

The above-described approach is known as a hard partition because the cluster membership is strict, i.e., each data point belongs to a single cluster. The alternative is a fuzzy partition, where every data point has a probability of closeness (in a range of 0 to 1) to each cluster. This approach is more realistic than hard partition since data points can belong to multiple clusters with varying degrees of likelihood, allowing for the representation of uncertainty and overlapping patterns in the cluster assignments. To incorporate fuzzy partition in the analyses, the fuzzy c-means algorithm was implemented through the cmeans function of the R package e1071 (Meyer et al. 2023). On each step of the divisive hierarchical approach, the fuzzy probabilities of each data point were recalculated for the full dataset and the new cluster assignments.

One crucial aspect of clustering is the specification of the number of clusters (k). We have circumvented this challenge using hierarchical k-means clustering. Although all obtained levels of clustering are valid and comparable, some results are notably more optimal. The criterion for this

optimality depends on the metric selected. In this case, we have chosen to analyse both results from the sum of squares (WSS and BSS) and silhouette score. This approach has enabled us to identify the three most representative numbers of ecosystems. The silhouette score measures how similar an object is to its own cluster (intra-cluster similarity) compared to other clusters (inter-cluster dissimilarity). It is calculated as the average silhouette coefficient for all points in the dataset, providing a way to assess the quality of clustering by quantifying the compactness and separation of the clusters. It ranges from -1 to 1. A score closer to +1 indicates that the clustering configuration is appropriate, with well-defined clusters. Conversely, a score near -1 suggests that the clustering may have been inappropriate, with points possibly assigned to the wrong clusters. A score around 0 indicates overlapping clusters or points at the decision boundary between clusters. Due to computational resource limitations imposed by the dataset size, 100 random samples of size 10,000 were iteratively generated to calculate the silhouette score from the R package *fpc* (Hennig 2023).

Other R libraries were used for data manipulation and visualization, including *bigmemory* (Kane et al. 2013), *tidyr* (Wickham et al. 2023), *ggplot2* (Wickham 2016), *gridExtra* (Auguie 2017), *patchwork* (Pedersen 2024), *sf* (Pebesma 2018), *rnaturalearth* (Massicotte and South 2023), *raster* (Hijmans 2023), *dggridR* (Barnes and Sahr 2023), and *exactextractr* (Baston 2023).

Results

The three-dimensional mapping of the ecosystems was achieved by clustering of nine environmental variables (Table 1) summarized into five principal components (Supplementary Table 2 and Supplementary Figure 1). The divisive hierarchical k-means clustering resulted in an exponential increase in cluster compactness and separation, as evidenced by the decreasing WSS and the corresponding increasing BSS (Table 3 and Supplementary Figure 2). The selected clustering levels were level 2 ($k=3$), level 6 ($k=7$), and level 23 ($k=24$). These solutions exhibit peaks in the silhouette score and a notable increase in WSS (accompanied by a decrease in BSS). For instance, $k=3$ is the first point where WSS exceeds BSS, indicating better-defined clusters compared to $k=2$. Levels 6 through 9 show similar WSS/BSS values, but level 6 exhibits the highest silhouette score. At levels 19 and 23, the silhouette score peaks again before decreasing, while WSS and BSS show a significant improvement at these points, which is minor thereafter (Supplementary Figure 2). The environmental differences between ecosystems become smaller at increasing clustering levels (Supplementary Figure 3).

The ecosystems extend through various depths, revealing environmental similarities from surface waters to the seabed (Figure 1). The area of each unit decreases across levels. If considered as perfect squares, the side length averages about 38 km at level 2, 25 km at level 6, and 13 km at level 23. In the broader classification (level 2), three distinct patterns emerge across different depths. Unit 1 maintains a consistent presence, ranging from 13.55 to 39.92 % across the depths. Unit 2 starts strong at 62.46 % in surface waters, drop to less than 1 % below 500 m, and slightly increase to 4 % at the seabed. Unit 3 dominates below 250 m, beginning at 50 m, and increasing its share to 86 % at 2,500 m, covering 77 % of the seabed. At level 6, only Ecosystems 4 and 5 are common across all depths. However, Unit 4 is proportionally the most significant in the deep sea (below 200 m), while Unit 5 dominates at 75 m. Ecosystems 1-3 are more important in shallow waters, with the first decreasing to less than 1 % below the surface layer, the second below 75 m, and the third below 150 m. Unit 6 starts to appear just below the surface, at 25 m, while Unit 7 appears at 50 m. The latter is very important in deep waters. The seabed at this level was highly dominated by Ecosystems 4 and 7. Finally, the global view at level 23 become more complex due to the increasing number of ecosystems. Generally, Ecosystems 6 and 7 are common across depths, with proportions varying from close to zero to 7.53 and 6 %, respectively. Ecosystems 1 and 8 are very important in the surface layer (25 and 47 %), but

they drop below 1 % at 25 m and 75 m, respectively. The most relevant ecosystems in the deep sea are Ecosystems 12, 13, 16, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23, and 24, each surpassing 10 %.

Level 2

The geographic distribution of the three resulting ecosystems across various depths is illustrated in Figure 2 and Supplementary Figure 4. In shallow waters, at 0 and 25 m, the results are almost identical. The first ecosystem is confined to high latitudes in both hemispheres, as well as the Black Sea and the Baltic Sea. The second ecosystem extends across tropical and most temperate regions, while the third unit has a marginal presence in the Arctic Ocean. Below 25 m, this third unit begins to expand significantly in high latitudes, particularly in the Southern Ocean, but also in the Sea of Okhotsk, Hudson Bay, and the four main western boundary upwelling systems: the Humboldt or Peru, California, Benguela, and Canary Currents. Below 50 m, the third unit continues to expand its range from these areas. By 100 m, it nearly encompasses the entire Baltic Sea, and by 250 m, it also spreads throughout the Black Sea. Below 750 m, the second unit is confined to the Mediterranean Sea, while the first unit is limited to the North Atlantic and Arctic Oceans. Interestingly, the first unit expands its extent in the North Atlantic from surface waters down to 2,500 m depth. The seabed exhibits a pattern like that at 2,500 m depth, with unit 1 being significantly more restricted, and unit 2 encircling some continental regions, primarily in the Atlantic and Indian Oceans. Concurrently, the fuzzy probabilities oscillate between 0.33 and 1. The lowest fuzzy probabilities are observed in the area occupied by unit 1 at shallower depths, whereas the expansion of the third unit clearly delineates the boundaries of these ecosystems. Below 750 m, lower values are also prominent in the Southern Hemisphere, despite this region being completely dominated by the third unit. It is only at 1,500 m and on the seabed that low values outline the mid-Atlantic ridge.

Ecosystem 1 is characterized by moderate nitrate and phosphate concentrations, fostering potential productivity. Dissolved molecular oxygen levels are relatively high, ensuring adequate oxygenation. The pH levels tend to be slightly alkaline. Total phytoplankton levels are moderate. Salinity levels are relatively high. Meanwhile, ocean temperatures vary within a temperate range but are notably lower compared to the other ecosystems. Conversely, Unit 2 displays lower nitrate and phosphate concentrations, potentially indicating reduced productivity. Dissolved oxygen levels remain moderate, with slightly higher pH levels and a significant presence of phytoplankton, suggesting increased productivity. Salinity levels are notably higher. Ocean temperatures remain stable and slightly warmer. In contrast, Unit 3 exhibits distinct features such as the deepest mixed layer among the ecosystems and comparatively high nitrate and phosphate levels, although with lower dissolved oxygen concentrations. pH levels tend to be slightly acidic, and phytoplankton presence is moderate. Salinity and temperature are moderate, with minimal sea ice cover.

Level 6

The geographic distribution of the seven resulting ecosystems through depths is shown in Figure 4 and Supplementary Figure 5. The surface layer is not very different from level 2. Unit 1 of level 2 has subdivided into ecosystems 1, 3, and 6, while unit 2 has subdivided into ecosystems 2 and 5. Thus, in the surface layer, three ecosystems are more prominent. Ecosystems 2 of both levels are nearly identical at this depth, while ecosystems 1 and 3 extend to higher latitudes. Unit 6 appears at 25 m in both northern and southern latitudes but is more prominent at greater depths in temperate and cold regions. Upwelling areas are also notable at this level, primarily marked by a combination of ecosystems 4 and 7, which are subdivisions of unit 3. Both 4 and 7 dominate in the deep sea. Unit 5 appears as a subdivision of unit 2, and at deeper waters below 500 m, it delineates confinement to the Mediterranean Sea. However, with its maximum proportion at 75 m depth, it defines tropical and subtropical areas below the surface. On the other hand, fuzzy probabilities range from 0.16 to 1 at this

level, indicating lower values than in unit 2. In general, their distribution closely follows the boundaries between ecosystems.

Ecosystem 1 is characterized by moderate nitrate and phosphate concentrations. Dissolved molecular oxygen levels are relatively high, ensuring adequate oxygenation. The pH levels tend to be slightly alkaline. Total phytoplankton levels are moderate. Salinity levels are relatively high. Meanwhile, ocean temperatures vary within a temperate range but are notably lower compared to the other ecosystems. Conversely, Unit 2 displays lower nitrate and phosphate concentrations, potentially indicating reduced productivity. Dissolved oxygen levels remain moderate, with slightly higher pH levels and a significant presence of phytoplankton, suggesting increased productivity. Salinity levels are notably higher. Ocean temperatures remain stable and slightly warmer. Unit 3 exhibits distinct features such as the deepest mixed layer among the ecosystems and comparatively high nitrate and phosphate levels, although with lower dissolved oxygen concentrations. pH levels tend to be slightly acidic, and phytoplankton presence is moderate. Salinity and temperature are moderate, with minimal sea ice cover. Unit 4 displays lower nitrate and phosphate concentrations, along with relatively low dissolved oxygen levels. Salinity and temperature are moderate, with minimal sea ice cover. Unit 5 exhibits moderate nitrate levels and relatively low phosphate concentrations, with stable ocean temperatures and minimal sea ice cover. Dissolved oxygen levels are moderate, with slightly higher pH levels and a significant presence of phytoplankton, indicating potential productivity. Salinity levels are notably higher. Finally, Unit 6 features moderate nitrate levels and relatively high phosphate concentrations, with stable ocean temperatures and minimal sea ice cover. Dissolved oxygen levels are moderate, with slightly higher pH levels and a significant presence of phytoplankton, indicating potential productivity. Salinity levels are relatively high.

Level 23

The geographic distribution of the 24 resulting ecosystems through depths is shown in Figure 6 and Supplementary Figure 5. Unit 1 in level 2 is represented in level 23 by nine ecosystems: 1, 4, 5, and 10 through 14, as well as 19. Meanwhile, unit 2 in level 2 is now subdivided into ecosystems 2, 3, 8, 9, 20, and 22 in level 23. Ecosystems 3, 5, 6, 7, 14, 15, and 17 are notably small, each spanning less than 10% of any depth. Among them, ecosystems 6 and 7 are the only ones present across all depths. Surface waters in the tropics and subtropics are relatively stable, primarily represented by unit 8, which covers nearly 47% of the globe. This region is then subdivided in depth. In addition, fuzzy probabilities are lower compared to previous levels, ranging from 0.05 to 1.

Ecosystems 1, 3, 4, and 5 exhibit moderate to high nitrate levels, with dissolved oxygen concentrations generally above average, indicating potentially conducive conditions for marine life. Additionally, these ecosystems display varying levels of phosphate, salinity, and pH. Ecosystems 2, 8, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, and 23 present notable variations in nitrate and phosphate concentrations, dissolved oxygen levels, and pH. Some ecosystems feature higher phytoplankton levels, potentially indicating enhanced productivity, while others exhibit lower levels. Ecosystems 6 and 7 stand out for their relatively low nitrate and phosphate concentrations, along with moderate dissolved oxygen levels and pH. These ecosystems display distinct environmental characteristics compared to others, potentially influencing the composition and distribution of marine life. Ecosystems 11 and 12 demonstrate comparatively high nitrate levels, along with moderate to high dissolved oxygen concentrations and pH.

Discussion

In response to the question, 'How many marine ecosystems exist?' the answer depends on the scale of interest. This study presents three nested levels of increasingly finer scales (with three, six, and 24 ecosystems), which have been an effective division in terms of environmental variance. The number of ecosystems, however, is not confined to these levels but is primarily determined by the 0.25-degree resolution used here. This resolution is the smallest size at which a unit can be maintained without further subdivision. Each hierarchical level provides a basis for comparing ecosystems that exhibit similar environmental variances and allows different characteristics to emerge at various levels with the appearance of new ecosystems that were not previously evident at broader scales. Ultimately, this identification of ecosystems with distinct environmental characteristics creates a foundational framework for investigating biodiversity patterns, assessing climate change vulnerability, and guiding ecosystem-based management approaches, such as the design of ecologically representative Marine Protected Areas (MPA).

The proposed classification is contingent upon the selected environmental variables and facilitates comparisons across included depth layers. Consequently, a regional classification focused exclusively on surface waters or encompassing a subglobal area yields divergent outcomes. While comparisons with previous classifications are valuable, identical patterns should not be anticipated. For example, the seven surface clusters identified by Zhao et al. (2019) markedly differ from our level 6, as only five of the seven clusters correspond to surface waters. Still, similarities emerge at higher latitudes such as our unit 1 aligning with their ecosystems 5 (Arctic Ocean) and 7 (Antarctic shelf), and our unit 3 correlating with ecosystem 2 (offshore Southern Ocean and North Pacific). However, even at level 23, we did not observe matching patterns in the divisions of tropic and subtropic regions or coastal areas. On the other hand, the 37 EMUs (Sayre et al. 2017) exhibit closer resemblance to our ecosystems. They exhibit more clustering in surface waters compared to level 23, yet unit 3 is absent. Below the surface, there is a general agreement in the shapes of the ecosystems, which follow the upwelling systems. However, these are defined by more ecosystems in this classification, likely due to the inclusion of additional variables. In both classifications, the Atlantic shows more variation at depths of 750-800 m than other basins. Nevertheless, the Atlantic is presented as a distinctive but uniform EMU below 1,200 m, whereas in our study, it is characterized by greater variation, probably due to the inclusion of seabed features.

The fuzziness levels found in the cluster boundaries indicate where the boundaries of ecosystems are broad and variable. This suggests the need for management approaches that consider the interconnectedness of these ecosystems, especially in regions of high fuzziness, recognizing the potential for both risks and benefits to spread across boundaries.

The ecosystem classification developed in this study offers a range of potential applications for marine research, conservation, and management. Like the IUCN's recent Global Ecosystem Typology (Keith et al., 2023), this work provides a foundational framework for examining spatial patterns of marine biodiversity at multiple spatial scales and depths. It can guide investigations into the drivers shaping community assembly and biodiversity patterns. Secondly, these ecosystems serve as valuable baseline units for monitoring temporal change, especially under the context of climate change or anthropogenic disturbances. By tracking shifts in environmental conditions within these ecosystems, researchers can assess the relative vulnerability of biodiversity to future changes, supporting proactive conservation planning. Thirdly, this classification can support ecosystem-based management approaches, particularly in the design and prioritization of MPAs. By ensuring MPAs encompass a range of ecosystems, they potentially maximize the diversity of habitats and species protected, enhancing resilience. Lastly, by delineating areas of distinct environmental conditions, this work can guide research efforts on species-environment relationships. This could inform predictive models of species

distribution shifts under future climate scenarios, supporting targeted conservation strategies for climate-sensitive species.

This study advances our understanding of global marine ecosystems by presenting a three-dimensional classification of the global ocean that extends from the ocean surface to the seabed. By focusing on the abiotic component, this work establishes a standardised classification of ecosystems based on environmental drivers shaping biodiversity. Importantly, by acknowledging limitations and highlighting avenues for refinement, this study underscores the iterative nature of ecosystem classifications and their potential to evolve through the incorporation of biotic data, higher temporal resolution, and alternative analytical approaches. The potential applications of this classification include biodiversity and climate change research, ecosystem-based management, and predictive modelling.

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Table 1. Pearson's correlation coefficient for the nine environmental variables: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (temp), pH, phosphate (phosph), phytoplankton (phyto), salinity, sea ice cover (sea ice) and mixed layer depth (mixed).

	Oxygen	Nitrate	Temp	pH	Phosph	Phyto	Salinity	Sea ice	Mixed
Oxygen	1	-0.40	-0.28	0.78	-0.43	0.29	-0.28	0.22	-0.30
Nitrate		1	-0.66	-0.79	0.97	-0.51	-0.09	-0.05	0.30
Temp			1	0.30	-0.65	0.44	0.37	-0.14	-0.19
pH				1	-0.81	0.47	0.02	0.10	-0.35
Phosph					1	-0.49	-0.17	-0.03	0.29
Phyto						1	-0.13	0.18	-0.63
Salinity							1	-0.26	0.09
Sea ice								1	-0.31
Mixed									1

Table 2. Result of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The first five principal components (PC1-5) recovered 95 % of the variance in the data matrix.

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9
Standard deviation	2.00	1.39	1.10	0.85	0.83	0.54	0.34	0.21	0.15
Proportion of variance	0.44	0.22	0.13	0.08	0.08	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00
Cumulative proportion	0.44	0.66	0.79	0.87	0.95	0.98	0.99	1.00	1.00

Table 3. Result for the first five levels of clustering to show the functioning of the divisive hierarchical k-means approach. TSS: Total sum of Squares. WSS: Within Sum of Squares. BSS: Between Sum of Squares. The number of clusters (N Clusters) increases one unit on each iteration, while TSS is kept constant, WSS decreases and BSS increases. The cluster size is given in number of cells. In red, the cluster subdivided in the consecutive step. The average length refers to the side of the cell.

Level	N Clusters	TSS	WSS	BSS	Cluster size	Average area (m ²)
						Average length (km)
1	2		99,3350	60,5972	4,227,840	2,171,838,102
					5,193,232	46
2	3		77,580	82,3520	2,638,758	1,447,892,068
					2,554,474	38
					4,227,840	
3	4		59,871	100,061	186,741	1,085,919,051
					2,554,474	
					2,452,017	33
					4,227,840	
4	5	159,933.2	48,650	111,282	186,741	868,735,241
					2,554,474	
					2,452,017	29
					2,529,812	
					1,698,028	
5	6		39,541	120,391	186,741	723,946,034
					880,360	
					2,452,017	
					2,529,812	27
					1,674,114	
					1,698,028	

Figure 1. Proportional size of ecosystems with depth for three hierarchical levels: level 2 (k=3), level 6 (k=7) and level 23 (k=24).

Depth 0

Depth 200

Depth 1000

Seabed

Figure 2. Ecosystems obtained by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions on level 2 of a divisive hierarchical k-means clustering of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 8 km wide for representation. Only four out of 15 depth layers included in the clustering are represented. Colour scale defines the three distinctive clusters identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.5 to 1) of each data point (right).

Figure 3. Environmental characteristics of the three identified clusters on level 2. Eight variables are represented: nitrate, dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), pH, phytoplankton, phosphate, salinity, and ocean temperature. The mixed layer depth and sea ice cover are not represented for being binary.

Depth 0

Depth 200

Depth 1000

Seabed

Figure 4. Ecosystems obtained by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions on level 6 of a divisive hierarchical k-means clustering of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 8 km wide for representation. Only four out of 15 depth layers included in the clustering are represented. Colour scale defines the three distinctive clusters identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.5 to 1) of each data point (right).

Figure 5. Environmental characteristics of the three identified clusters on level 2. Eight variables are represented: nitrate, dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), pH, phytoplankton, phosphate, salinity, and ocean temperature. The mixed layer depth and sea ice cover are not represented for being binary.

Depth 0

Depth 200

Depth 1000

Seabed

Figure 6. Ecosystems obtained by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions on level 23 of a divisive hierarchical k-means clustering of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 8 km wide for representation. Only four out of 15 depth layers included in the clustering are represented. Colour scale defines the three distinctive clusters identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.5 to 1) of each data point (right).

Figure 7. Environmental characteristics of the three identified clusters on level 2. Eight variables are represented: nitrate, dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), pH, phytoplankton, phosphate, salinity, and ocean temperature. The mixed layer depth and sea ice cover are not represented for being binary.

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Variable distribution in the dataset before clustering. Each of the five variables corresponds to a principal component (PC1-5) preserved after PCA. The variables are normalized.

Supplementary Figure 2. The upper panel displays the Total Sum of Squares (TSS), the Within-Cluster Sum of Squares (WSS), and the Between-Cluster Sum of Squares (BSS) for the first 99 levels of clustering using the divisive hierarchical k-means approach. The lower panel illustrates the silhouette values for each clustering level, obtained from 100 random samples of 10,000 data points each. The number of clusters (N Clusters) increases by one unit in each iteration, culminating in 100 clusters. The optimally selected clusters ($k=3$, $k=7$, and $k=24$) are marked with dotted lines.

Supplementary Figure 3. Environmental Euclidean distance between 100 clusters after the first 99 levels of clustering using the divisive hierarchical k-means.

Depth 0

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 25

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 50

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 75

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 100

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 150

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 200

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 250

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 500

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 750

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 1000

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 1500

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 2000

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 2500

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Seabed

1 2 3

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Supplementary Figure 4. Ecosystems obtained by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions on level 2 of a divisive hierarchical k-means clustering of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 8 km wide for representation. All 15 depth layers included in the clustering are represented. Colour scale defines the three distinctive clusters identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.5 to 1) of each data point (right).

Depth 0

Depth 25

Depth 50

Depth 75

Depth 100

Depth 150

Depth 200

Depth 250

Depth 500

4 5 6 7

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 750

4 5 6 7

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 1000

4 5 6 7

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 1500

4 5 6 7

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 2000

4 5 6 7

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Depth 2500

4 5 6 7

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Seabed

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1.0

Supplementary Figure 5. Ecosystems obtained by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions on level 6 of a divisive hierarchical k-means clustering of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 8 km wide for representation. All 15 depth layers included in the clustering are represented. Colour scale defines the three distinctive clusters identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.5 to 1) of each data point (right).

Depth 0

Depth 25

Depth 50

Depth 75

Depth 100

Depth 150

Depth 200

Depth 250

Depth 500

Depth 750

Depth 1000

Depth 1500

Depth 2000

Depth 2500

Seabed

Supplementary Figure 6. Ecosystems obtained by hard (left) and fuzzy (right) partitions on level 23 of a divisive hierarchical k-means clustering of environmental data. Data disaggregated into equal-area hexagons 8 km wide for representation. All 15 depth layers included in the clustering are represented. Colour scale defines the three distinctive clusters identified by hard partition (left), or the maximum fuzzy probabilities (range from 0.5 to 1) of each data point (right).

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